

Novel Synthetic Polyflavonyls

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Flavonols have been methylenated with methylene iodide to provide Bi-(flavonyloxy)-methanes. Similar attempts of methylation of these flavonols with iodoform have resulted in the successful synthesis of Tri-(flavonyloxy)-methanes, a novel class of poly-flavonyls. The structures (ii and iii) proposed have been confirmed by analytical and spectral data.

Methylenation of flavonoids observed in nature¹⁻⁵ has also been carried out by Seshadri and coworkers⁶ in the laboratories, who reported the successful synthesis of biflavonyls in which two flavonoid units are interlinked through a methylene dioxy group, involving phenolic hydroxyl groups at position 7 and 4' or through a methylene group between 5 and 8 positions.

(ii)

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|---|--|
| (i) a. R = R' = R'' = H | (i) d. R = CH ₃ , R' = H, R'' = OCH ₃ |
| (i) b. R = R' = H, R'' = OCH ₃ | (i) e. R = H, R' = R'' = OCH ₃ |
| (i) c. R = CH ₃ , R' = R'' = H | (i) f. R = CH ₃ , R' = R'' = OCH ₃ |
| (ii) a. R = R' = R'' = H | (ii) d. R = CH ₃ , R' = H, R'' = OCH ₃ |
| (ii) b. R = R' = H, R'' = OCH ₃ | (ii) e. R = H, R' = R'' = OCH ₃ |
| (ii) c. R = CH ₃ , R' = R'' = H. | (ii) f. R = CH ₃ , R' = R'' = OCH ₃ |

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Now we have succeeded in synthesising new type of biflavonyls in which two flavonoid units are linked through a methylene dioxy group, but the formation involves the enolic hydroxyl group (3) instead of the phenolic ones. Flavonols (I) suitably substituted in 6,3',4' positions have been methylenated by methylene iodide to Biflavonyloxymethanes (ii).

The yields of the products have been found to be quite low. The structures have been confirmed on the basis of molecular weight, microanalytical data and absence of phenolic test. U.V., I.R. and NMR spectral data are also in agreement with the proposed structure (ii). Mass spectrum of (ii b.) exhibits characteristic peaks at m/e , 281 (corresponding to fragment X (ii b) 267 (Y fragment in ii b), 251, 236 along with other peaks. In this case however, the parent ion peak is not observed as it is not expected of a compound containing two other oxygen atoms separated by a single carbon atom⁷.

Triflavonyls of the type in which the three flavonoid units are linked to one central carbon atom have neither been reported from natural sources nor have been synthesised so far. Encouraged with the methylenations of flavonols we undertook the methylation of these compounds on similar lines resulting in the formation of triflavonyloxymethanes (iii), a novel class of pol flavonyls. A series of five compounds (iii a, b, c, d and f) have been synthesised, starting with suitably substituted flavonols which have been condensed with iodoform in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in dry acetone. The structures have been confirmed on the basis of microanalysis, molecular weights, absence of phenolic test and spectral data like I.R., U.V. and NMR.

(iii)

(iii) a. $R = R' = R'' = H$ (iii) b. $R = R' = H; R'' = OCH_3$ (iii) c. $R = CH_3; R' = R'' = H$ (iii) d. $R = CH_3; R' = H; R'' = OCH_3$ (iii) e. $R = CH_3; R' = R'' = OCH_3$

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To our surprise when only a methyl group is present in 6 position of the flavonol molecule methylation resulted into a biflavonyl (ii c) instead of the expected triflavonyl (iii c). The reason for this unexpected and interesting observation is under study. However, the attempts to condense flavonols with chloroform or bromoform under similar conditions to get triflavonyloxy methanes have failed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Synthesis of Biflavonyloxy methane (ii a) : Flavonol (1.8 g.) was refluxed in dry acetone (50 ml.) with methylene iodide (1.2 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (8 g.) for 10 hours till a negative ferric chloride test was observed. The reaction mixture was cooled and filtered. The potassium carbonate was washed with acetone (20×3 ml.). The filtrate and the washings on recovery of the solvent provided a dark red viscous liquid which quickly solidified on cooling. Repeated crystallisations from methanol provided a colorless cluster of needles (0.5 g.) m.p. 185–86°. (Found : C, 75.8; H, 4.1%; mol. wt. 472; C₃₁H₂₀O₆ requires C, 76.2; H, 4.09%; mol. wt. 488).

Compounds iib and iif were also synthesised in a similar manner. Their properties are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Biflavonyloxy methanes (ii)

Com- pound	m.p.	Cryst. from	% yield	Formula	Found%		Mol. Wt.	Required%		Mol. Wt.	Spectral and other data
					C	H		C	H		
ii b. ^a	188–89°	Benzene	36	C ₃₃ H ₂₄ O ₆	71.4	4.2	514	72.3	4.3	548	†
ii c.	230–31°	-do-	20	C ₃₃ H ₂₄ O ₆	76.9	4.3	490	76.7	4.65	516	
ii d.	255–56°	-do-	20	C ₃₅ H ₂₆ O ₈	72.4	4.5	588	72.9	4.5	588	
ii e.	195–98°	Benzene, EtOAc (1 : 1)	20	C ₃₅ H ₂₆ O ₁₀	72.4	4.5	588	72.9	4.6	608	
ii f.	202–203°	Benzene	17	C ₃₇ H ₃₂ O ₁₀	69.3	4.8	593	69.8	5.03	636	

† $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 238 m μ (log ϵ 4.012) and 320 m μ (log ϵ 4.036).

$\gamma_{\max}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1640, 1470, 1370, 1250, 1176, 1036 (methylene dioxy group) 980, 900, 833 and 752 cm⁻¹.

NMR spectra show proton signals at 1.95 (methylene protons), 2.2–3.7 (aromatic protons) and 6.5 (methoxyl protons) τ , these values are corroborated by the integration curve.

Synthesis of Triflavonyloxymethane iii a^b : Flavonol (1 g.) was refluxed with iodoform (0.6 g.), dry acetone (40 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (10 g.) for 18 hrs. till a negative ferric chloride test was obtained. The reaction mixture was filtered and the residue washed with acetone (30×20 ml.). The filtrate and washings were mixed and the solvent recovered to provide a red viscous liquid which could not be crystallised. However, on filtration over alumina (Brookman Grade I, 10 g.) using benzene as an eluent, a pale yellow residue was obtained from the first four fractions (20 ml. each). TLC revealed the

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presence of only one component in these fractions. Repeated crystallisations from ethanol provided a colorless crystalline substance (50 mg.) m.p. 138° (Found : C, 75.7; H, 4.1; mol. wt. 692; $C_{46}H_{28}O_9$, requires, C, 76.2; H, 3.9% and mol. wt. 724).

Compounds iii b, c, d and f were synthesised in a similar manner. The properties of these compounds are recorded in Table 2 below.

TABLE 2

Triflavonyloxy methanes (iii)

Com- pound	m.p.	Cryst. from and appearance	% yield	Formula	Found%		Required%			Spectral	
					C	H	mol. wt.	C	H		mol. wt.
iiib.	128-29°	EtOH, Flappy white.	19	$C_{49}H_{34}O_{12}$	71.8	3.8	768	72.2	4.1	814	†
iiic.	found to correspond with the biflavonyl (iic).										
iiid.	114-15°	Benzene, colorless	2	$C_{52}H_{40}O_{12}$	72.3	4.3	802	72.8	4.6	856	
iiif.	118-19°	MeOH, granular solid pale yellow.	1.5	$C_{55}H_{46}O_{15}$	69.49	5.56	896	69.7	4.85	946	*

† $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 340 m μ (log ϵ 3.88).

$\gamma_{\max}^{\text{KBr}}$ at 1613, 1493, 1460, 1389, 1282, 1250, 1205, 1176, 1145, 1111, 1036, 909, 826 and 752 cm^{-1} .

Its NMR spectra show proton signals at 1.75-3.05 (methinic and aromatic protons) 6.12 (methoxy protons) τ and the values are corroborated by the integration curve.

* $\gamma_{\max}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1603, 1492, 1418, 1264, 1315, 1257, 1160, 1140, 1111, 1020, 854, 812, 806 and 780 cm^{-1} .

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